

"The effect of plant extracts on multi-drug resistant bacteria"

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Abstract

This study investigated the antimicrobial activity of the ethanolic extract of *Capparis spinosa* flower and *Cinnamom cassia* barks against various types of multidrug-resistant bacteria (MDR) from various infection sites. 48 specimens were collected from patients at Fallujah Teaching Hospital, Fallujah Teaching Hospital for Women and Children, and private labs. 27 specimens showed positive cultures and gave 27 bacterial isolates, and antibiotic susceptibility tests were performed to determine multidrug resistance. 11 isolates were identified as MDR bacteria. The ethanolic extractions of *C. spinosa* flowers and *C. cassia* barks were performed using Soxhlet and evaluated in vitro using the agar well diffusion method. The most common microorganisms isolated from UTI and GITI were *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *C. spinosa* extract showed positive results in 7 out of 11 (63.64%) MDR bacteria, while cinnamon extract showed positive results in 8 out of 11 (72.7%). The ethanolic extracts of *C. spinosa* flower and *C. cassia* bark showed significant antimicrobial activity against MDR bacteria, suggesting that they could be used as alternatives to antibiotics in the future. Further studies are needed to determine the active components responsible for the observed antimicrobial activity and evaluate the safety and efficacy of these extracts in vivo.

Keywords: Multi-drug resistant bacteria (MDR), Bacterial infections, Ethanolic extract, *Capparis spinosa*, *Cinnamom cassia*, Antibacterial activity

Introduction

Bacterial infection is a major threat to human health around the world, it causes a local infection (e.g. impetigo); or systemic infection (e.g. urinary tract infection). Bacterial infection can be treated by antibiotics which are substances active against bacteria either killing them or inhibiting their biological activities [1]. The first antibiotic was Penicillin which was discovered in 1928 by Alexander Fleming when he found that his "mould juice" was able of inhibiting a wide range of harmful bacteria, such as streptococcus, meningococcus and the diphtheria bacillus. Over time and due to the widespread use of antibiotics some pathogenic bacteria became resistant to Penicillin, In 1940, Abraham and Chain reported that an *E. coli* strain was able to inactivate penicillin by producing penicillinase (β -lactamase nowadays), day by day scientists have noticed the increase in the number of bacteria resistant to more antibiotics, researchers displayed one of among the first reports of multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacteria was of *Shigella* resistant to sulphonamides, streptomycin, chloramphenicol, and tetracycline in Hong Kong in 1955 [2]. Multi-drug resistant bacteria now is one of the biggest problems facing the healthcare system, and perhaps by the 2030s or 2040s of this century, no effective antibiotic will remain. To solve this problem, the world is turning to alternative solutions like Nano drug-based therapeutics, antimicrobial proteins, bacteriophages, probiotics etc. In our research project, we decided to go with another solution, which is the use of medicinal plant extract to heal bacterial infection, and we tried to prove its efficiency in killing or inhibiting bacterial infection. Historically, medicinal plants were used thousands of years ago, the earliest record of its use was about 3000 B.C.E by the Sumerian civilization, where hundreds of medicinal plants were used [3].

Aims of study

This study aimed to isolate and identify the bacterial etiology of infections including UTI and GITI, and to demonstrate the development of antibiotic resistance in the causative bacteria. Additionally, the study sought to identify the most antibiotic-sensitive and resistant bacterial isolates from infected patients, extract active ingredients from medicinal plants (Cinnamon cassia and *Capparis spinosa*), and observe and determine the effect of these extracts on multi-drug resistant bacteria.

2.1 Multidrug resistant bacteria (MDR)

Multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria pose a significant threat to global health due to their resistance to multiple antibiotics. This resistance makes them challenging to treat with conventional therapies, especially in healthcare settings where immunocompromised patients are at higher risk. MDR bacteria, such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE), and carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* (CRE), cause infections like pneumonia, bloodstream, urinary tract, and skin infections. The rise of MDR bacteria is a global issue, affecting both developed and developing countries, particularly in healthcare facilities. Infections caused by MDR strains often result in prolonged hospital stays, increased healthcare costs, and higher mortality rates. The primary driver of MDR is the overuse and misuse of antibiotics, including incomplete courses of treatment and inappropriate prescriptions for viral infections. The abuse of antibiotics in animal feed also contributes to this issue. Currently, treatment of MDR infections relies on last-resort antibiotics, but resistance to these drugs is increasing. The development of new antibiotics is slow, and pharmaceutical companies are investing less in this area due to high costs and limited profitability [4].

2.2 The most common multi-drug resistant bacteria

Klebsiella pneumoniae, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

2.2.1 The pseudomonads group

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, the main pathogen in this group, is a Gram-negative, motile bacterium often found in moist environments and hospital settings. It is typically part of the normal human flora but causes infections in immunocompromised individuals.

Morphology: Rod-shaped, Gram-negative, and motile, typically found in pairs or chains.

Culture: Produces characteristic pigments like pyocyanin (blue) and pyoverdine (green). It grows well at 37–42°C, differentiating it from other *Pseudomonas* species.

Growth Characteristics: Aerobic and oxidase-positive, known for producing various pigments and mucoid colonies, especially in cystic fibrosis patients.

Pathogenesis: It becomes pathogenic when it enters areas with compromised defences (e.g., burn wounds, catheterized areas). It is resistant to numerous antimicrobials due to biofilm arrangement and other destructiveness components like toxins and enzymes [5].

2.2.2 *S. aureus*

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive bacterium that causes a variety of infections in both hospital and community settings, including Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA). It is normally found in human nasal flora but can lead to serious infections if it enters the bloodstream or tissues

Morphology: Gram-positive cocci that grow in clusters, commonly found on skin and mucous membranes.

Culture: Golden-yellow colonies on media, grows in high salt concentrations.

Identification Tests: Catalase-positive, coagulase-positive (to distinguish *S. aureus* from other *Staphylococcus* species), and mannitol fermentation-positive [6].

Pathogenesis: Causes infections like skin infections, pneumonia, and toxic shock syndrome.

Virulence factors include biofilm formation, toxin production, and immune evasion mechanisms [7].

2.2.3 *P. mirabilis*

Proteus mirabilis is a Gram-negative, facultative anaerobe known for its swarming motility and ability to form biofilms. It is part of the human intestinal flora but can cause infections, especially in the urinary tract [8].

Morphology: Gram-negative rod, known for swarming on culture media.

Culture: Forms pale colonies on MacConkey agar and shows swarming on blood agar [9].

Pathogenesis: Causes urinary tract infections by adhering to epithelial cells via pili, producing urease, and motility. These factors contribute to its pathogenicity, particularly in kidney infections [10].

2.2.4 *K. pneumoniae*

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a Gram-negative, encapsulated bacterium that causes nosocomial infections, particularly in immunocompromised patients, such as those with diabetes or alcohol use disorder. It commonly affects the lungs, leading to pneumonia [11].

Morphology: Short, plump, Gram-negative rods, encapsulated and non-motile.

Culture: Grows on Nutrient Agar and MacConkey Agar, producing pink colonies due to lactose fermentation [12].

Pathogenesis: Causes pneumonia and other invasive infections. Virulence factors include its capsule, which protects it from phagocytosis, and endotoxin production, contributing to its high degree of virulence.

2.3 Antibiotic

Antibiotic is an antimicrobial substance effective against microorganisms. It is the most vital sort of antibacterial agent for fighting bacterial diseases, and antibiotic medicines are broadly utilized in the treatment and prevention of such infections. They may either killing or repress the development of microscopic organisms.

2.3.1 Mechanisms of Action of Antibiotic

Antibiotics exert their effects through several mechanisms, the most common being inhibition of cell wall synthesis, followed by inhibition of protein synthesis (translation). Other mechanisms include alteration of cell membranes, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, and .antimetabolite activity

.23 1.1. Inhibition of Cell Wall Synthesis

Most bacterial cells are protected by a rigid layer of peptidoglycan (PG), which shields them from osmotic pressure and environmental conditions. To survive, bacteria synthesize peptidoglycan using trans-glycosylases and trans-peptidases. Antibiotics like penicillin, carbapenems, and cephalosporins block the cross-linking of PG by inhibiting these enzymes.

Glycopeptide antibiotics, such as vancomycin, inhibit bacterial growth by binding to PG units and blocking trans-glycosylase and trans-peptidase activity.

.23 1.2. Inhibition of Protein Synthesis

Protein synthesis in bacteria involves the transcription of DNA into mRNA (transcription) and the subsequent translation of this mRNA into proteins by ribosomes. The bacterial ribosome consists of two subunits, 30S and 50S, and antibiotics target one of these subunits to inhibit protein synthesis.

.23 1.3. Inhibitors of the 30S Subunit

Aminoglycosides: These antibiotics attach to the outer membrane of bacteria and enter through an energy-dependent active transport mechanism. Once inside, they bind to the 16S rRNA of the 30S subunit, causing misreading of mRNA and premature termination of protein synthesis.

Tetracyclines: These drugs, including doxycycline and minocycline, bind to the 16S rRNA of the 30S subunit, preventing the binding of tRNA to the A site and halting protein synthesis.

.23 1.4. Inhibitors of the 50S Subunit

Chloramphenicol: Hinders synthesis of protein by binding to the 23S rRNA of the 50S subunit, and preventing the attachment of tRNA to the ribosome.

Macrolides: These antibiotics, like erythromycin, target the 23S rRNA of the 50S subunit, blocking translocation and causing premature detachment of incomplete peptide chains.

Oxazolidinones: Linezolid, a synthetic antibiotic, interferes with protein synthesis at several stages by binding to 23S rRNA of the 50S subunit. It also suppresses 70S formation and interacts with peptidyl-tRNA [13].

.23 1.5. Inhibition of Membrane Function

Antibiotics in this class disrupt microbial cell membranes by creating pores, leading to leakage of cellular molecules, inhibition of respiration, and cell death. Gram-positive bacteria are generally resistant to these drugs due to their thick cell walls.

Example: Lipopeptides like polymyxins belong to this class of antibiotics [14].

.23 1.6. Disruptors of Metabolism (Folate Pathway Inhibitors)

This class of antibiotics inhibits the bacterial folic acid synthesis pathway, which is essential for the production of DNA and RNA building blocks.

Inhibition of Dihydrofolate Reductase: Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole acts by inhibiting the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase, which is essential for folic acid synthesis.

Substrate Competition: Sulfonamides and Dapsone compete with p-aminobenzoic acid (PABA), inhibiting the production of folic acid [15].

.23 1.7. Inhibition of Nucleic Acid Synthesis

Antibiotics in this category block the bacterial nucleic acid synthesis pathways, which are critical for replication and transcription. For example, quinolones inhibit the activity of topoisomerase II and IV, enzymes involved in DNA replication, leading to bacterial death [13].

2.4 Antibiotic resistance

Antimicrobial resistance in bacterial pathogens is a global challenge, leading to high

morbidity and mortality. Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria are showing multidrug resistance, making the treatment of infections increasingly difficult or impossible with conventional antibiotics. The lack of early identification of pathogens and their antimicrobial susceptibility often results in the overuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics, which exacerbates the problem [15].

2.4.1 Resistance can be described in two ways:

A- Natural (Intrinsic, Structural) resistance:

This type of resistance is based on the inherent structural characteristics of bacteria, not associated with antibiotic use. It occurs when the target structure of the antibiotic is absent or when the antibiotic cannot reach its target. For example, bacteria that are Gram-negative are naturally resistant to vancomycin because it can't pass via their outer membrane. Similarly, bacteria like *Mycoplasma* and *Ureaplasma*, which lack cell walls, are naturally resistant to beta-lactam antibiotics that inhibit cell wall synthesis [16].

B- Acquired resistance

Procured resistance emerges from genetic changes in bacteria, so they to become resistant to antibiotics they were previously sensitive to. This resistance often results from chromosomal mutations or the acquisition of extrachromosomal elements like plasmids and transposons [17].

2.4.2 Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance

Bacteria employ four main mechanisms to resist antibiotics: limiting the uptake of antibiotics, target modification, efflux pumps, and antibiotic inactivation

2.4.2.1 Limiting uptake of antibiotics

Bacteria, particularly Gram-negative organisms, can limit the uptake of antibiotics through structural barriers. The outer membrane and the LPS layer in Gram-negative bacteria act as a barrier to certain molecules. For instance, *S. aureus* can produce a thickened cell wall to limit vancomycin's entry, providing intermediate resistance. In *E. aerogenes*, mutations in porin channels result in resistance to imipenem and cephalosporins, while in *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, similar mutations confer resistance to β -lactams and tetracycline. Biofilms, which often involve *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* or other pathogens, protect bacteria from antimicrobial agents and facilitate horizontal gene transfer [18].

2.4.2.2 Target modification

Target modification provides resistance to various antibiotics, including β -lactams, glycopeptides, macrolides, and aminoglycosides. A common mechanism is the alteration of the peptidoglycan precursor from D-Ala-D-Ala to D-Ala-D-Lac or D-Ala-D-Ser, reducing the binding affinity for glycopeptides like vancomycin. The genes conferring vancomycin resistance (e.g., vanHAX) are often located on transposons, which can be found in both clinical strains and producer organisms, showing an evolutionary relationship. Furthermore, 16S rRNA methyltransferases grant aminoglycoside resistance by methylating particular ribosomal sites [19].

2.4.2.3 Efflux pumps

Efflux pumps (EPs) are membrane proteins that actively expel toxic compounds, including

antibiotics, from bacterial cells. These pumps recognize and expel harmful agents, preventing them from reaching their targets. Efflux pumps use energy derived from ATP or the proton motive force to transport these compounds against a concentration gradient [20].

2.4.2.4 Antibiotic inactivation

2.4.2.4.1 Antibiotic inactivation by hydrolysis

Some bacterial enzymes hydrolyze antibiotic bonds, inactivating the drugs. For example, extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) confer resistance to penicillins and cephalosporins.

2.4.2.4.2 Antibiotic inactivation by redox process

While less common, bacteria can inactivate antibiotics via oxidation or reduction. For instance, the enzyme TetX oxidizes tetracycline, and *Streptomyces virginiae* reduces a ketone group in virginiamycin M1, rendering it inactive.

2.4.2.4.3 Antibiotic inactivation by group transfer

Transferases inactivate antibiotics by adding chemical groups (e.g., acetyl, phosphoryl, or adenylyl) to key sites on the antibiotic molecule. This mechanism is seen with aminoglycosides, macrolides, and rifampicin, among others. These processes require co-substrates like ATP, acetyl-CoA, or NAD⁺.

2.4.3 Genetics of antibiotic resistance

2.4.3.1 Antibiotic resistance via mutations

Mutations in bacterial genes can lead to antibiotic resistance by altering the target of antibiotics. For illustration, mutations in *rpoB* and DNA topoisomerases cause resistance to rifampicin and fluoroquinolones. Mutations can also affect antibiotic uptake and efflux systems, as seen in the *OprD* porin of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

2.4.3.2 Antibiotic resistance via horizontal gene transfer

Horizontal gene transfer plays a vital role in antibiotic resistance spread. Resistance genes are transferred between bacteria via conjugation, transformation, or transduction. For instance, the CTX-M-15 β -lactamase gene, often found in *E. coli*, is associated with mobile genetic elements and is responsible for extended-spectrum resistance to β -lactams. This gene has spread globally and is linked to high-risk factors like prolonged hospitalization, catheterization, and prior antibiotic use [21].

2.5 Medicinal plants

2.5.1 History of using plants as antimicrobial

Long before the discovery of microbes, humans widely recognized the healing potential of certain plants, which we now know contain antimicrobial properties. Since ancient times, plants have been used to treat common infectious diseases, and many traditional remedies, such as bearberry (*Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*) and cranberry juice (*Vaccinium macrocarpon*) for urinary tract infections, continue to be used today. Other plants, like lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis*), garlic (*Allium sativum*), and tea tree (*Melaleuca alternifolia*), are regarded as broad-spectrum antibiotics [22].

The greatest benefits often come from the essential oils of these plants, which are particularly effective in treating infections of the respiratory, urinary, gastrointestinal, biliary, and cutaneous systems. For instance, tea tree oil is widely used to treat acne and skin infections [23].

Searching for new antimicrobial agents from plant-based has been a focus of ethnopharmacological research for decades. Future research should aim to obtain specific data on plant antimicrobial activity, guiding the isolation of active compounds based on known plant activities rather than using antimicrobial properties solely to support phytochemical studies.

2.5.2 Plants of study

2.5.2.1 Cinnamon

Cinnamon, native to Sri Lanka, is a widely used tropical spice obtained from the inner bark of *Cinnamomum* trees. Besides its culinary uses, cinnamon is known for its medicinal properties, including antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anticancer effects [24]. The most important volatile oils come from species such as *C. burmannii*, *C. cassia*, *C. verum*, and *C. zeylanicum*. These oils are used interchangeably by pharmaceutical manufacturers. Cinnamon contains secondary metabolites that exhibit antibacterial properties, such as cinnamaldehyde, cinnamic acid, and essential oils like trans-cinnamaldehyde and eugenol. Trans-cinnamaldehyde (TC) is responsible for most of the antibacterial activity, particularly due to its α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group [25]. Though some compounds like coumarin and cinnamyl acetate have low antibacterial activity, their mixture may produce synergistic effects, enhancing TC's antibacterial properties [26].

2.5.2.2 *Capparis spinosa*

Caper (Capparis spinosa L.) is a perennial plant native to the Mediterranean, commonly found in dry, rocky areas. It has been traditionally used for its antimicrobial, cytotoxic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, treating conditions such as diabetes, asthma, and rheumatism. *C. spinosa* contains bioactive compounds such as flavonoids (rutin, quercetin), glucosinolates, and tannins. Its flower buds are rich in volatile constituents, including isothiocyanates and sulphides, which contribute to its pharmacological effects [27,28].

2.5.3 Mechanisms of antibacterial action of Cinnamon

2.5.3.1 Alterations in the cell membrane and its lipid profile

Trans-cinnamaldehyde (TC) interacts with the bacterial cell wall by penetrating the phospholipid bilayer, binding to proteins, and disrupting their function. This leads to altered membrane permeability, cytoplasmic coagulation, and loss of essential metabolites and ions, causing cell damage [29].

2.5.3.2 Inhibition of ATPase

TC inhibits ATP synthesis by downregulating F1F0-ATPase, as observed in *Cronobacter sakazakii*. Studies on *E. coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes* showed that TC disrupts the proton motive force, leading to rapid ATP depletion and reduced bacterial growth [30].

2.5.3.3 Inhibition of cell division

TC interferes with bacterial cell division by inhibiting the polymerization of FtsZ, a protein essential for forming the Z-ring, which is necessary for cell division. TC prevents GTP-dependent FtsZ polymerization, disrupts Z-ring formation, and decreases cell division in *E. coli* in a dose-dependent manner [31].

2.5.3.4 Inhibition of membrane porins

TC reduces the expression of membrane porins, such as OmpA, OmpC, and OmpR, which are involved in active transport across bacterial membranes. This reduction affects bacterial resistance to osmotic stress and desiccation in *C. sakazakii*, likely due to decreased *ompC* and *ompR* gene expression [30].

2.5.3.5 Inhibition of motility and biofilm formation

TC exhibits antibiofilm activity against various bacterial species, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas sp.* TC inhibits biofilm formation by downregulating quorum sensing systems, which disrupts biofilm-associated communication molecules like PQS in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [32].

2.5.4 Mechanism of antibacterial action of Capparis

2.5.4.1 Mechanisms of action of flavonoids

Inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis by inhibiting topoisomerase and DNA gyrase that play essential roles in DNA replication, transcription, chromosome segregation, and recombination cytoplasmic membrane perforating it and/or reducing its fluidity, paralyze energy metabolism by inhibiting the respiratory chain and ATP synthase, prevent cell wall synthesis by acting as competitive, inhibition of biofilm formation [33].

2.5.4.2 Mechanisms of action of isothiocyanates

Disruption of the cell membrane, deregulation of enzymatic processes (β -galactosidase, ATPase, and AKP), inhibition of cellular (ATP, DNA, and proteins) and induction of heat-shock proteins as well as oxidative stress, and biofilm formation [34].

2.5.4.3 Mechanisms of action of sulphides

Inhibits the activity of catalase enzymes and superoxide dismutase that are connected to cellular defenses against oxidative stress. Consequently, it causes an elevation of the intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) content and a reduction of the glutathione levels causing membrane depolarization and lowering the ATP levels [14].

3. Materials and method

The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Fallujah / College of Applied Science, and all procedures were performed in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to sample collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables, including the prevalence of bacterial species and the susceptibility rates of MDR isolates to plant extracts, were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

3.1. Culturing

The bacterial isolates were cultured by using the streaking method, on the primary culture medium (Nutrient Agar, Blood agar) then on a differential medium (e.g. MacConkey Agar) and incubating for 24hrs at 37°C.

3.2 Identification of isolated bacteria

Bacterial isolates grown on MacConkey solid medium and solid blood agar medium were diagnosed according to each of the following grounds:

3.2.1 Cultural characteristics

Bacterial colonies were initially diagnosed based on their phenotypic characteristics such as the shape, color and size of the colonies, and appear hemolytic on blood agar, lactose fermentation or non-lactose fermentation on MacConkey agar.

3.2.2 Microscopic characteristics

The microscopic characteristics of bacterial cells were identified using Gram stain. A single pure colony was taken from the nutrient agar media using the sterile vector loop and placed on a glass slide and mixed with a few drops of sterile water and left to dry, then fixed by passing it over the flame quickly, then it was dyed with Gram stain then examining under a light microscope through an oil immersion objective lens, the arrangement and shape of bacterial cells were observed [35].

Figure 1 :

A. culturing bacterial isolates on primary culture media (Blood agar)

B : culturing bacterial isolates on a differential medium (MacConkey Agar)

C : Identifying bacterial Gram stain type under microscope

3.2.3 Biochemical tests

3.2.3.1 Catalase test

Transferring part of a newly-grown bacterial colony on a nutrient agar medium to a clean slide with a drop of water, then placing a drop of H₂O₂ on it at a concentration of 3%. The

result is positive when air bubbles appear, and this is evidence of oxygen liberation, and the result is negative in the absence of bubbles [36].

3.2.3.2 Oxidase test

In this test, a filter paper was moistened by adding drops of the previously prepared oxidase reagent, and then a part of the bacterial colony was transferred to the paper using a sterile carrier or sterile wooden sticks. The result is positive when the color turns to violet after 20-30 seconds, and the absence of violet color is considered a negative result.

3.2.3.3 Indole test

This test was carried out by inoculating tubes containing peptone water with bacteria and then incubating for 24 hours at a temperature of 37°C. After Adding Kovacs' reagent, when a red ring appears on the top layer seconds after adding the reagent the result is positive [37].

3.2.3.4 Methyl red test

This test was carried out by inoculating tubes containing MR. medium with a portion of a pure bacterial colony and incubated for 24 hours at a temperature of 37°C. After the incubation period, some drops of methyl red were added to the tubes, the color that appeared red indicates acid production and a positive result, while the yellow color indicates that the result is negative [38].

3.2.3.5 Citrate utilization test

This test is performed through the inoculation of the sterile tube that contains Simmons citrate agar medium by a colony of pure bacteria, and then this tube is incubated for 24 hours, if the color medium changes from a green color to blue color this means the citrate is consumed by bacteria as a single recourse of carbon, if there is no change in color medium this mean negative result [39].

Figure 2 : A. catalase B. Indole test C. Methyl red test D. Citrate utilization test

3.2.3.6 Urease test

The test is performed by inoculation of tubes that contain slant urea medium in a way streaking and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C, the change in medium color from yellow color to pink indicates a positive result and when no color change is negative [40].

3.2.3.7 Sugar fermentation

This test is performed by tubes that contain (TSI) agar medium are inoculated by a colony of bacterial, colonies in a way of streaking, then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Alteration in the deep portion of the medium from ruddy color to yellow implies a positive result for the fermentation of only glucose, if the alteration in the whole medium from red color to yellow indicates to fermentation of lactose and sucrose and gas been in the form of bubbles in the bottom of the tube if bacteria form hydrogen sulfide gas a black precipitate will appear in bottom of tube [41].

Figure 3 : A. Urease test B. Sugar fermentation

3.2.3.8 Coagulase test

Coagulase is an enzyme that clots blood plasma. This test is performed on Gram-positive, catalase positive species to distinguish the coagulase positive *Staphylococcus aureus*. Coagulase enzyme considered a virulence factor of *S. aureus*. The clot formation around an infection caused by this bacteria protects it from phagocytosis. *Staphylococcus aureus* can be differentiated from other coagulase negative *Staphylococcus* species in this test. [42].

3.2.4 Storage of bacterial isolates

Using information from the manufacturer, prepare the nutrient agar and sterilize in an autoclave for 15 minutes at 1 atm and 121°C, then put it in a test tube in slant and inoculated with a bacterial colony and late in the incubator for 24 hours in 37°C then preserved in the fridge with packaging Para film. [43].

3.2.5 Antibiotic susceptibility test

Antibiotic sensitivity was tested by the disc method Kirby-Bauer method [44]. Several bacterial colonies growing on a nutrient medium were transferred to a test tube containing 2 ml of distilled water to form a bacterial suspension, and the bacterial suspension was measured using a MacFarland device at a scale of 0.5, then the solution was placed on a plate

containing Muller Hinton agar that prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions, left for a minute and then removed excess. Then using sterile forceps to place the antibiotic discs on the surface of the medium and then incubated for 18 hours at a temperature of 37 °C, the diameters of the antibiotic disc were measured in millimeters and using a graduated ruler and then compared with the international measurements table (CLSI 2023).

Figure 4 : A. coagulase test B. Antibiotic susceptibility test

3.3 Medicinal plants

3.3.1 Collection of plant material

A- *Capparis spinosa*

From local Iraqi gardens in Rawah/ Anbar/ Iraq, *C. spinosa* flowers were collected at the end of the Summer season (September to October) in 2022. *C. spinosa* flowers were collected and washed up thoroughly in water, dried in the shade at room temperature, cut into small pieces and grinded until they became a fine powder.

B- *Cinnamon cassia*

From an Iraqi local market, *Cinnamon cassia* barks were bought. Barks were bought dry and then grounded into a fine powder.

3.3.2 Extraction of active ingredients

A- *Capparis spinosa*

The dried *Capparis spinosa* flower was ground into a fine powder for the preparation of the alcoholic extract. 60 grams of the capers flower powder were then transferred into a one-liter flask using a Soxhlet extractor at 45 °C, and hydroalcoholic extract [ethanol 70% (500 ml)] was added to keep the powder level covered. The solution was filtered after 72 hours, and the ethanolic extract was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator apparatus at 50 °C with a turn speed of 70 rpm and put the extract in petri-dish glass then placed in the incubator at 37 °C [45].

B- *Cinnamon cassia*

The dried *Cinnamon cassia* bark was ground into fine powder for the preparation of the alcoholic extract. 60 grams of the bark powder were transferred into a one-liter flask using a Soxhlet extractor at 60°C, and hydroalcoholic extract [ethanol 70% (500 ml)] was added to keep the powder level covered. The solution was filtered after 48 hours, and the ethanolic extract was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator apparatus at 40°C with a turn speed of 70 rpm and put the extract in a petri-dish glass then placed in the incubator at 37°C [46].

3.4 Dilution of extract

The extract was solved into distilled water, and 1g of the extract was dissolved into 5ml of D.W. which made a 20% solution of plant extract. This concentration passed through serial dilution until we reached the minimum concentration we used (0.625%). The serial dilution factor was 1, 1ml of the 20% was transferred via pipette into a tube containing 1ml of D.W which made the concentration 10%, this process continued until we had 0.625% in the fifth tube.

3.5 Applying extracts on the bacterial isolates

Among our isolates of bacteria, 11 of them showed multi-drug resistance (MDR). These 11 isolates were taken to apply the plant extract on. The chosen bacteria were activated by sub-culturing on Brain Heart Infusion agar to reach the highest vitality, after sub-culturing the dishes were incubated in a 37°C incubator for 24 hours. By using a loop, three to five colonies of each bacteria were transferred into a tube containing 3ml of normal saline and spread by sterile swab on Muller Hinton Agar medium to do the test. The test was carried out using well diffusion method [47]. 5 wells were made in each dish, one was for control filled by D.W to ensure there is no leak in the medium. The remaining four wells were filled with different concentrations of solution (5%, 2.5%, 1.25%, 0.625%). The dishes incubated for 18hrs at 37°C and then the results were read and measured. The zone of inhibition was measured by using a role in millimeter unit and determined as a positive result (showed an inhibition) and a negative result (which showed a resistance).

Figure 5 : A. *Capparis spinosa* flower buds B. *Capparis spinosa* powder

C. Soxhlet extractor D. ethanolic extracts of *Capparis spinosa*

4.Result & Discussion :

Among 48 specimens collected from patients in Fallujah Teaching Hospital and Fallujah Teaching Hospital for Maternity and Children and private labs, 27 bacterial isolates were collected and represented as 56.25% of the total samples.

Table : Distribution of Clinical Specimens and Culture Results

Specimen Source	Total Collected	Positive Growth	Negative Growth
Urine (UTI)	30	17	13
Stool (GITI)	18	10	8
Total	48 (100%)	27 (56.25%)	21 (43.75%)

Urinary tract infection:

Urinary tract samples were the dominant type of samples (17 out of 48 different isolates, which means 35.417% of total isolates) due to the high incidence, and recurrent nature of UTIs, coupled with the convenience of collecting urine samples, makes UTI samples more frequently collected than other types of samples.

A significant number of UTIs have been diagnosed by physicians as recurrent urinary tract infections (14 out of 17 isolates, about 82.35%). Furthermore, a small percentage of these recurrent UTIs present as multi-drug resistant (6 out of 14, about 42.86%), this percentage is less compared with previous study conducted by [48], that studied the predominance of multidrug-resistant bacteria causing urinary tract infections among men with prostate enlargement attending a tertiary hospital in dar es salaam,tanzania (77.3%), and more compared with study conducted by [49], that studied the plant-derived antimicrobials (PDAMs) to control urinary tract infections (28.6%), this discrepancy is due to several reasons, the most important of which are our bacterial UTI isolates are few (17),other reason is differences in the study population; the prevalence of MDR bacteria in patients with recurrent UTIs can vary depending on the demographics of the study population, such as age, gender, and underlying health conditions, and changes in antibiotic use or infection control practices; the prevalence of MDR bacteria can also be influenced by changes in antibiotic use or infection control practices over time [50].

Table : antibiotic sensitivity test for urinary tract infection

Bacteria isolate	AZM	MEM	F	CIP	NA	AK	CTX	CN	RA
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	I	S	R	I	R	R	R	S	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	R	S	S	I	R	S	R
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	S	S	I	S	S	I	R	S	R
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	S	R
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	S	S	R	I	S	R	R	S	R
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	I	R
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	S	S	R	S	S	S	I	S	R
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	S	S	S	S	S	S	I	S	R
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	S	S	I	I	R	I	I	S	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	I	R	S	S	S	R	S	I
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	I	S	S	I	R	S	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	I	S	S	S	R	S	R
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	S	S	S	S	S	S	I	S	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	I	S	S	S	R	S	R
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	R	S	R	S	S	I	I	S	R
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	I
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	S	S	R	S	S	S	I	S	R

Note. AK: Amikacin; AZM: Azithromycin; CIP: Ciprofloxacin; CN: Gentamicin; CTX: Cefotaxime; F: Nitrofurantoin; MEM: Meropenem; NA: Nalidixic Acid; RA: Rifampicin

Table 2: Prevalence of Multi-Drug Resistant (MDR) Isolates

Isolate Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Multi-Drug Resistant (MDR)	11	40.7%
Non-MDR	16	59.3%
Total Positive Isolates	27	100%

Gastrointestinal tract infection:

In our research, gastrointestinal tract infection (GITI) samples were the second most commonly collected samples after UTI samples (10 out of 48, about 20.83%) because of the high incidence of GITIs, coupled with the ease of collection and diagnosis, makes GITI samples the second most commonly collected samples after UTI samples in healthcare settings. Following antibiotic susceptibility testing of gastrointestinal tract infection isolates, a notable proportion of these bacteria were found to exhibit resistance to multiple classes of antibiotics (6 out of 10, about 60%) and have been considered as a multi drug resistant bacteria, this percentage is less compared with a previous study conducted by [51], that studied the Infection with a high proportion of multidrug-resistant bacteria in conflict-related injuries is associated with poor outcomes and excess resource consumption: a cohort study of Syrian patients treated in Jordan (73.47%), and less compared with a previous study conducted by [52], that studied Multidrug Drug Resistance of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* Isolated from Iraqi Patients and Microbiota (72%). In our study and compared to other studies we found that approximately 60-70 % of GITI are caused by multi drug resistant bacteria, the common reasons are the random taking of antibiotics, person-to-person transmission, poor infection control practices, underlying medical conditions, poor sanitation, emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance genes, poor healthcare infrastructure and environmental factors [53], and according to Centers for Disease Control World Health Organization.

NO. of bacteria	Bacteria isolate	CIP	CTX	CN	MEM	AK	IPM	C	VA	RA	AZM
1.	<i>K.oxytoca</i>	S	R	R	S	I	S	R	R	R	S
2.	<i>E.coli</i>	S	R	I	S	I	S	I	R	R	S
3.	<i>E.coli</i>	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	S
4.	<i>P.mirabilis</i>	S	R	R	I	R	S	S	I	I	S
5.	<i>k.pneumoniae</i>	S	R	R	S	I	I	R	R	R	S
6.	<i>k.oxytoca</i>	S	R	R	S	I	S	R	R	R	S
7.	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	S	R	I	S	I	S	S	I	I	S
8.	<i>k.oxytoca</i>	S	R	I	S	S	S	S	S	I	S
9.	<i>P.mirabilis</i>	S	S	I	S	I	S	R	I	I	S
10.	<i>k.oxytoca</i>	S	R	I	S	I	S	S	S	I	S

Note. AK: Amikacin; AZM: Azithromycin; C: Chloramphenicol; CIP: Ciprofloxacin; CN: Gentamicin; CTX: Cefotaxime; IPM: Imipenem; MEM: Meropenem; RA: Rifampicin; VA: Vancomycin.

Multi-drug resistant bacteria:

As we mentioned previously we have collected 27 bacterial isolates from different infections sites and after doing the antibiotic susceptibility 11 isolates were found to be multi-drug resistant bacteria the proportion of these to the total number of isolates are (44.4%), this percentage is less compared with study conducted by [54]. That studied the prevalence of multidrug resistant bacteria in postoperative wound infections at Tikur Anbessa specialized hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (65.5%) and more comparable with study conducted by [55], that studied the access- and non-access-related infections among patients receiving

haemodialysis: experience of an academic centre in oman (31.0%), as shown approximately 40-45% of these isolates identified as multi-drug resistant bacteria, these high percentages may be attributed to several reasons, the most important of which are overuse and misuse of antibiotics, poor infection control practices, lack of awareness and education, environmental factors including poor sanitation and contaminated water sources and exposure to animal feces, cross-border transmission, lack of access to effective antibiotics, spread of antibiotic resistance genes [56].

Plant extract:

A- *Capparis spinosa*:

As previously mentioned, 11 isolates from different infection sites were identified as multi-drug resistant bacteria. Subsequently, the ethanolic extract of *Capparis spinosa* was tested against these isolates, and the resulting findings are presented below.

Table :

The ethanolic extract of <i>Capparis spinosa</i>									
UTI	concentration				GITI	concentration			
	5%	2.50%	1.25%	0.63%		5%	2.50%	1.25%	0.63%
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	S	R	R	R	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	S	R	R	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	R	R	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	R	R	R	R
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	S	S	R	R	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	S	S	R	R
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	R	R	R	R	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	R	R	R	R
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	R	R	R	R	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	S	S	S	R
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	S	S	S	S					
Total	11								

The results are less comparable to a study conducted by [57], which studied the effect of Caper (*Capparis spinosa*) extracts as a natural antimicrobial agent (100% activity against all bacteria) and also less comparable with a study conducted by [58], that studied the antibacterial synergistic effect of extracts of the organs of *Capparis spinosa* in combination with antibiotics. (100% activity against all bacteria).

B- Cinnamon cassia

Table :

The ethanolic extract of <i>Cinnamon cassia</i>									
UTI	concentration				GITI	concentration			
	5%	2.50%	1.25%	0.63%		5%	2.50%	1.25%	0.63%
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	S	S	R	R	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	R	R	R	R
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	S	S	S	R	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	S	S	R	R
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	R	R	R	R	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	S	S	R	R
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	R	R	R	R	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	S	S	S	R
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	S	S	S	S	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	S	S	S	S
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	S	S	S	R					
Total	11								

Table : Comparative Efficacy of Ethanolic Extracts against MDR Bacteria

Bacterial Species	Capparis spinosa	Cinnamon cassia
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (3)	2 (S) / 1 (R)	3 (S) / 0 (R)
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> (4)	3 (S) / 1 (R)	3 (S) / 1 (R)
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> (4)	2 (S) / 2 (R)	2 (S) / 2 (R)
Total Susceptible MDR Isolates	7 (63.6%)	8 (72.7%)
Total Resistant MDR Isolates	4 (36.4%)	3 (27.3%)

Figure : A. effect of *Cinnamomum cassia* extract on *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from UTI
 B. effect of *Capparis spinosa* extract on *Proteus vulgaris* from UTI
 C. effect of *Capparis spinosa* extract on *Escherichia coli* from GITI

These results are less compared to a study conducted by [59], that studied the anti-oxidant, antibacterial, anti-biofilm, and anti-quorum sensing activities of four essential oils against multidrug-resistant bacterial clinical isolates (95.24%), there were a specific types of bacterial isolates showed commonalities in terms of resistance (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Escherichia coli*), resistance of these three bacteria in our study is may be attributed to several potential molecular mechanisms through which bacteria could resist the antimicrobial effects of Capparis and Cinnamon extract. One possibility is that the extract is unable to penetrate the cell wall or membrane of the bacteria, preventing it from reaching its target site within the cell [60,58]. Additionally, bacteria may be able to modify or degrade the active compounds in the extract through enzymatic or other metabolic processes [61,62]. Bacteria may also be able to actively pump out the extract or its active compounds through efflux pumps [63,64], which can help the cells maintain their internal environment and protect against toxins. Finally, bacteria may be able to adapt or evolve over time to develop resistance to the extract through genetic mutations or horizontal gene transfer [65].

5.1 Conclusions

Multi-drug resistant bacteria (MDR) are defined as acquired non-susceptibility to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial categories. In this study, MDR bacteria accounted for 40.74% of all bacterial isolates diagnosed (11 of 27). The most common microorganisms causing infections were *K. oxytoca* and *P. vulgaris*, accounting for 12/27 (56.25%), and no significant relationship was found between sex or age and infection caused by MDR bacteria. Among the antibiotics tested, meropenem showed the highest sensitivity for most bacteria, while rifampicin was the most resistant antibiotic across isolates. Most MDR bacteria were sensitive to both extracts at the highest concentration, while some showed complete resistance at all concentrations tested.

5.2 Recommendation

Performing bacterial culture for infections and doing sensitivity tests. Attempting to prevent pharmacies from giving antibiotics without a prescription, as well as spreading medical awareness to reduce the random use of antibiotics which is the most important cause of bacterial resistance to antibiotics. Doctors are advised to reduce the prescribing of any third-generation antibiotic of cephalosporin because of resistance for most isolated bacteria. We recommend researchers who have a similar interest in the contents of our research to expand the field of study of more plants and observe their effectiveness against bacteria. We recommend incorporating plants which have antimicrobial affectivity to their diet (especially Capparis and Cinnamon).

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